

EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITY AND THE STAGES OF THEIR FORMATION

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6526843>

Xujakulova Ra'no Sharipovna

*Senior lecturer at the Department of Uzbek and Russian languages,
Tashkent financial Institute, Uzbekistan*

Abstract: *Research conducted by many psychologists, as well as Uzbek psychologists, allows us to identify the most essential qualities for modern teachers. In this case, the professogram of the teaching profession (a short and comprehensive document that is systematized, studied by labor psychologists and intended for use in future practice) is called a professogram.*

Key words: *Professional skills, analysis, teacher, law and order, practice, student ability, career guidance.*

Introduction: The role of the teacher and his responsibilities determine the importance of the attention paid by society and the public to the work of educating the younger generation.

It is known that the most important qualities of a teacher, which are related to his personality and professional qualities, are:

- The teacher's devotion to his homeland, love for children, the desire to bring them up in the spirit of humanity, love of his country, mother tongue, history of its people and its culture, living in the idea of state independence;
- High sense of social responsibility; self-control, patience, endurance, tenacity;
- The basic requirements of the society to the teacher are: spiritual and enlightenment of the individual, knowledge of the essence of the national awakening ideology and the wealth of mankind, education of children in the spirit of independence, loyalty to their ideas, love for nature and family; to have extensive knowledge, to be aware of different knowledge;
- Young pedagogical psychology has a deep knowledge of social psychology and pedagogy, youth physiology and school hygiene; to know children, to understand their inner world;
- Have a solid knowledge of the subject he teaches, be aware of new achievements and shortcomings in the world of science in his profession, subject; mastering the methods of education and upbringing;
- Creative approach to their work;

- Pedagogical technique has logic (speech, expressive means of teaching) and pedagogical tactics;

- Continuous improvement of their knowledge and pedagogical skills; Every teacher must strive to be able to fully meet these requirements.

In addition to the demands of society, the teacher must keep in mind what is expected of those around him, the school administration, colleagues, teachers and their parents.

Method and materials: We, the teachers of the Department of Psychology, studied about a thousand students and received a written answer from them to the question of whether you know the mood of your teacher and how his mood affects you.

94.2% of students reported being able to know the teacher's mood, while 89.8% said they were strongly influenced by the teacher's mood. It was also asked to indicate which of the following reasons (poor self-esteem, poor self-esteem: bad mood of the teacher; poor comprehension of the lesson material; poor preparation for the lesson) had the worst effect on the student's mood. Many students noted that the teacher was in a bad mood. —How does the teacher's mood affect you? The answer to the question was also very meaningful.

Answer: If the student is in a good mood, you will not suffer much from your failures,

- Lesson will not be so boring,

- Difficult thing will be easy,

- You will not know that time has passed in the lesson, and so on, answers.

Especially if it is bad?

- Hands don't work,

- You lose self-confidence,

- You want to run away from school, and even

- My brain freezes.

Individual style in teaching. The success of educational work depends in many respects on the pedagogical ability and interest of the teacher. M.G. Davletshin points out that some mental processes and features of the teacher, in which the personality traits of the teacher are so complex that it can be called pedagogical ability. Pedagogical ability consists of a number of qualities that are characteristic of a teacher's personality - his intelligence, will, emotions, character and other characteristics. Education - the ability to work is not an innate ability, man inherits these abilities from nature. The ability of the individual to the ability develops in the process of activity. Teaching requires great attention and observation in the educational work of the teacher.

Result and discussion: The teacher must have the sensitivity, the ability to observe, which is characteristic of true educators. Any observation is made on the basis of thorough attention. Careful review of teachers' written work requires the teacher to have an extremely strong and deep focus. Features of teacher speech. Students acquire knowledge primarily through the teacher's live speech. The teacher's speech should be correct in terms of vocabulary, phonetics, pronunciation, sentence structure, emphasis in words, and so on. In a speech, ideas should be consistent, logical, well-founded, and convincing.

Features of teacher thinking. Teacher thinking is mainly reflected in the independent planning and systematic presentation of teaching materials.

The teacher should explain the teaching materials using inductive and deductive methods. At the same time, the teacher must teach students to draw conclusions independently of the facts and to understand some facts and conclusions based on the general rules, rules and concepts. The teacher is able to connect abstract concepts with concrete concepts.

The qualities of the teacher's thinking, such as content, speed, breadth, are also reflected in the fact that children express their knowledge clearly, meaningfully, clearly. Willpower qualities of the teacher. Pedagogical activity is an activity related to the orientation in accordance with the goals of education and overcoming many difficulties. That is why this activity requires a lot of willpower.

VI. The inculcation of the ideology of national independence in the hearts and minds of young people is carried out through various forms of education. The following tasks should be considered:

Creation of a differential pedagogical, psychological program to inculcate the ideology of national independence in educational institutions in accordance with the age of children and students;

Goal taxonomy. The content of vocational education.

The teaching process creates good conditions for the separation of educational and developmental goals, the acquisition of knowledge and the formation of the necessary personal qualities. In the process of acquiring knowledge in the classroom, views and spiritual qualities are also formed, that is, the unity and interdependence of these functions is observed.

Another aspect of the content of the educational function of teaching is the mastery of evidence-based learning material. The realization of the educational purpose of teaching depends on the nature of the knowledge imparted to the students. The more clearly the educational goal is set and the more relevant it is to the teaching material received in the lesson, the easier it will be to choose the

method of teaching in the lesson. The set of educational goals of teaching also consists of skills that are formed on the basis of the given knowledge, and the nature of knowledge is determined by the relevant skills.

Conclusion

The educational purpose of teaching is to form positive attitudes and beliefs, morals, willpower and emotions in students. The teacher performs a certain aspect of the educational task in the process of teaching the teaching material in each lesson. The formation of worldview, moral qualities, feelings, willpower, etc. of a person is a continuous process and cannot be divided into clearly limited parts. The results of the educational goal are not as specific and clear as the results of the educational goal. The educational goal is realized differently in different students. The educational purpose of the lesson is to form certain moral, aesthetic, emotional and volitional qualities in the personality of the student. The study of any learning material affects the development of the student, the development of thinking logic, cognitive powers and learning motives in him. Achieving a developmental goal of teaching is similar to achieving an educational goal. The most important thing in fulfilling the task of perfection, as in the realization of the educational goal, is to form the desire of the student to perfection. In one lesson, it is impossible to set and implement the task of analysis, logical methods of synthesis, the development of abstract thinking skills, the formation of active and independent thinking. Achieving the goal of perfecting a lesson involves constantly planning specific ideas and developing the logic of thinking, activism, and an interest in learning.

Basic terms or basic concepts (basic concepts) are the basic information in the training material. Basic phrases also arise and are used in planning or restructuring the subject being studied. Mastering the learning material also depends mainly on mastering the basic phrases (basic concepts).

Basic phrases can also be found frequently in other topics in the study material. Therefore, it is convenient to study the study material based on basic phrases.

REFERENCES:

1. XAITBAYEVNA NOSIROVA, M. (2021). ANALYSIS OF MORPHOLOGICAL (TIPOLOGICAL) CLASSIFICATION OF LANGUAGES *European Journal of Life Safety and Stability* (2660-9630), 7, 155-157. Retrieved from <http://www.ejlss.indexedresearch.org/index.php/ejlss/article/view/106>

2. Saidova, Makhsudakhon Abbasovna WAYS TO EVALUATE THE PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF TEACHERS AND ITS FORMATION // ORIENSS. 2021. №Special Issue 2. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/ways-to-evaluate-the-professional-competence-of-teachers-and-its-formation> (дата обращения: 24.03.2022).

3. Абдуллаева Марҳабо Раҳмонкуловна, (2020). 'ИНСОНИЯТНИНГ ЎЗАРО МУНОСАБАТИДАГИ МИЛЛИЙ КОЛОРИТНИ ИФОДАЛОВЧИ ФЕЪЛИ ФРАЗЕМАЛАР (Агата кристи асарлари талкинида)' "МАРКАЗИЙ ОСИЁДА ЛЕКСИКОЛОГИЯ ВА ЛЕКСИКОГРАФИЯ: АНЪАНАЛАР ВА ҲОЗИРГИ ЗАМОН ИЛМИЙ МАКТАБЛАРИ" республика илмий-амалий конференцияси илмий тўплами, 153-158.

4. 4.Javliyeva Dilafruz Rustam qizi. (2021). THE COMMUNICATIVE NATURE OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK KINSHIP TERMINOLOGY. *Archive of Conferences*, 14(1), 3-4. Retrieved from <https://conferencepublication.com/index.php/aoc/article/view/604>

5. 5.Akramxodjaeva, D., M. Nasretdinova, and M. Abdullayeva. "Translation of national events and concepts in fiction." *International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research* 9.2 (2020): 2984-2986.

6. Abduganiyevna, Akramxodjayeva D. "Effective Teaching of a Foreign Language Through a Contextual Approach." *JournalNX*, vol. 6, no. 10, 2020, pp. 180-181.

7. Abdujabborova Kamola Husniddin Qizi IMPROVING LITERACY SKILLS THROUGH LEARNING READING // Наука и образование сегодня. 2021. №4 (63). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/improving-literacy-skills-through-learning-reading> (дата обращения: 16.03.2022).

8. ХАЙТБАЙЕВНА NOSIROVA, M. (2021). ANALYSIS OF MORPHOLOGICAL (TIPOLOGICAL) CLASSIFICATION OF LANGUAGES. *European Journal of Life Safety and Stability* (2660-9630), 7, 155-157. <http://www.ejlss.indexedresearch.org/index.php/ejlss/article/view/106>

9. Абдуллаева Марҳабо Раҳмонкуловна, (2020). 'ИНСОНИЯТНИНГ ЎЗАРО МУНОСАБАТИДАГИ МИЛЛИЙ КОЛОРИТНИ ИФОДАЛОВЧИ ФЕЪЛИ ФРАЗЕМАЛАР (Агата кристи асарлари талкинида)' "МАРКАЗИЙ ОСИЁДА ЛЕКСИКОЛОГИЯ ВА ЛЕКСИКОГРАФИЯ: АНЪАНАЛАР ВА ҲОЗИРГИ ЗАМОН ИЛМИЙ МАКТАБЛАРИ" республика илмий-амалий конференцияси илмий тўплами, 153-158.

10. Абдуллаева Марҳабо Раҳмонкуловна, (2019). 'Ingliz tilidan O'zbek tiliga ilk bevosita tarjimalarda mazmun va shakl mutanosibliği' "Termiz Davlat Universiteti. "ADABIY ALOQALAR VA MADANIYATLARNING UZARO TASIRI" Xalqaro ilmiy konferensiya to'plami, 237-239
11. Zilola Xabibullayevna Abidova (2022). INGLIZ VA O'ZBEK TILLARIDAGI TAFAKKUR FE'LLARINING TAHLILI. Scientific progress, 3 (2), 736-739.
12. Rishatovna B.K., Utkurovna I.G, Habibullaevna A.Z, Maratovna K.Z, Kakhramonovna M.D. "Modern foreign popular music as a means of teaching an english language to students of a non-linguistic profile." International journal of psychosocial rehabilitation, (2020). ISSN: 1475-7192.
13. Akramxodjaeva, D., M. Nasretdinova, and M. Abdullayeva. "Translation of national events and concepts in fiction." International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research 9.2 (2020): 2984-2986.